

Aligning the HOSA with EOSC

HOSA

Author Mark van de Sanden (SURF)
Contributors Menno Scheers (SURF), Tom van Veen (SURF), John van den Berge (SURF), Peter Leijnse (SURF), Klaas Wierenga (GEANT)
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1 Introduction

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Higher Education Sector Architecture (“Hoger Onderwijs Sector Architectuur”, HOSA) are both initiatives focusing on strengthening the collaboration across stakeholders and sectors. SURF colleagues have been and are actively involved in projects supporting the development of EOSC and in establishing HOSA. The contributions from SURF in both initiatives have been mostly independent, without active cross-collaboration. From a high-level perspective, EOSC and HOSA have similar aims but differ in detail, in approach, and state of practice. To keep research and the e-infrastructure of the Netherlands at the international forefront, it is essential to keep the national e-infrastructure internationally connected. EOSC is one of the main European initiatives supporting research within Europe, while HOSA has the same aim at the national level. This report has been developed on request from Hans Louwhoff, Chief Operations Officer from SURF, and Menno Scheers, Lead Enterprise Architect of SURF and lead architect of HOSA) in order to assess the alignment between HOSA and EOSC.

1.1 Scope

To enable the development and uptake of Open Science in Europe, the European Commission (EC) has proposed the creation of a European cloud for Open Science. EOSC will essentially involve the federation of existing research data infrastructures and the realisation of a Web of FAIR Data and Related Services for Science, making research data interoperable and machine-actionable following the FAIR guiding principles¹. EOSC is not a single monolithic organisation or resource provider but is rather a federation built out of many independent organisations and resource providers as in a ‘System-of-Systems’ approach. To support interoperability and composability, an EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) will be established as the glue to connect different kinds of resources that are provided across both thematic domains and infrastructure boundaries.

As education and research performing organisations are increasingly collaborating, it is expected that more and more communal facilities will be created and need to be integrated. To ensure these communal facilities are in line with the higher education sector, sectoral architectural frameworks are required. The HOSA project started in 2020 to develop these sectoral architectural frameworks. In this context of the HOSA project, domain architectures have been developed for “Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning”, “Research Data Management”, and “Identity and Access Management”. Because the initial focus of EOSC is to support scientific research, the focus of this alignment is focused on the domain architecture of Research Data Management, which aims at supporting researchers throughout the research lifecycle.

EOSC and HOSA are complementary to each other and should be aligned where relevant, with the aim of HOSA to develop national sectoral architectural frameworks and the aim of EOSC to develop an Architecture and interoperability framework at European level.

1.2 Assignment

The aim of this report is to assess the potential synergies between EOSC and HOSA and to ensure alignment of the standards and guidelines that are promoted by EOSC and HOSA.

¹ <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

The following objectives have been defined for the assignment:

- Make a comparison between the aims and objectives of EOSC and HOSA
- Analyse the state of the art and target state of EOSC and HOSA
- Identify principles and proposed guidelines in the scope of EOSC to be included in HOSA and visa-versa

The main outcomes are:

- Defined change proposal for the next version of the HOSA Research Data Management domain architecture, including input from EOSC
- Advice on which EOSC standards can be used at the national level as well
- Advice on what components SURF can deliver at the national level that can also be used at a European level and
- A proposal to structurally align EOSC and HOSA in the future

1.3 Process

To assess EOSC and HOSA, a desk research study has been performed on HOSA. Because EOSC is initially concentrated on supporting research and research communities, the desk research has focused on the Research Data Management domain architecture. To discuss the alignment in more detail, four workshops were held between May and July 2022 to address the following topics:

1. Introduction to EOSC
2. Principles, Stakeholders, and Governance
3. Platform Architecture and Platform components
4. Recommendations

The workshops were held between:

- Menno Scheers, Tom van Veen, John van den Berge, Peter Leijnse, SURF Enterprise Architects
- Klaas Wierenga², Chief Information & Technology Officer at GEANT, chair of EOSC Future Technical Coordination Board (TCB), member of the EOSC Association Task Force (TF) on Interoperability between Data and Services
- Mark van de Sanden, Technical Specialist Data Preservation Services Team, Technical Coordinator EUDAT, member of the EOSC Future Strategy and Oversight Board (SOB) and TCB, member of the EOSC Association TF on Interoperability between Data and Services

1.4 How to read this document

This report can be read as a standalone document, although many references to external documentation are included. To create a standalone document, sections from external documentation are included “as is” and are referenced and marked in *italic*.

The alignment of HOSA with EOSC is described from different angles and will be of interest to different audiences. Table 1 provides a quick overview with reading suggestions.

² <https://www.linkedin.com/in/klaaswierenga/>

Table 1 How to read this document

If you are interested in ...	Please read section ...
An overview of this report	Executive Summary
Scope, background of the assignment, process and people involved	Section 1
A short introduction to EOSC and HOSA	Section 2
The alignment at Enterprise Architecture (EA) level of principles, stakeholders and governance	Sections 3.1 Principles, 3.2 Stakeholders, 3.3 Governance
A comparison between EOSC and HOSA platform architecture, platform core components, and categories of services made available through the platforms	Sections 3.4 Platform Architecture, 3.5 Platform core components, 3.6 Platform offered services
Platform interoperability and aspects of the exchange of resources between platforms	Section 3.7 Platform interoperability, 3.8 Exchange of resources between HOSA and EOSC
International architecture and platform initiatives	Section 4
The recommendations	Section 5
A recap and final conclusions	Section 6

2 Introduction to EOSC and HOSA

In general, EOSC and HOSA are familiar acronyms. Given their separate development histories, however, it is not expected that the readers of this report are familiar with the background and details of the EOSC and HOSA initiatives. Therefore, short introductions are provided on EOSC and HOSA.

2.1 EOSC

The initiative to develop EOSC was first mentioned in a blog from Günther Oettinger, published on June 22 2015³. The blog was written after a session on open science at the conference “Opening up to an ERA of Innovation”. The announcement was made in the context of the Digital Single Market as⁴:

In the context of the Digital Single Market Strategy, we will soon be launching a European Open Science Cloud initiative which will combine existing and future data infrastructures, offering secure and seamless access to European researchers for storing, managing, and processing data from different sources.

After the initial blog, the official announcement to develop EOSC was made in the official communication of the EC on “European Cloud Initiative – Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe”⁵.

The European Cloud Initiative builds on the Digital Single Market (DSM) Strategy, which aims, inter alia, to maximise the growth potential of the European digital economy. It aims to develop a trusted, open environment for the scientific community for storing, sharing and re-using scientific data and results, the European Open Science Cloud. It aims to deploy the underpinning super-computing capacity, the fast connectivity and the high-capacity cloud solutions they need via a European Data Infrastructure. Focussing initially on the scientific community, the user base will be expanded to the public sector and industry, creating solutions and technologies that will benefit all areas of the economy and society. Achieving this will require a collaborative effort open to all those interested in exploiting the data revolution in Europe as an essential component of global growth.

After the announcement, the development of EOSC was initiated via different calls in the Horizon2020 work programme. EOSCpilot⁶ was the first project to support the first phase in the development of EOSC. The aims were:⁷

- *Propose and trial governance frameworks for the EOSC and contribute to the development of European open science policy and best practices;*
- *Develop a number of demonstrators functioning as high-profile pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to show interoperability and its benefits in a number of scientific domains; and*
- *Engage with a broad range of stakeholders, crossing borders and communities, to build the trust and skills required for the adoption of an open approach to scientific research.*

³ <https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vjuzkm9mvyy4>

⁴ Reference 3, paragraph 4

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0178&from=PL>, Introduction, paragraph 6

⁶ <https://eoscipilot.eu/>

⁷ <https://eoscipilot.eu/about/eoscipilot-brief>

After EOSCpilot, more than 30 projects have been contributing to the development of EOSC, see Figure 1. SURF has been active in many of these projects (e.g. EOSCpilot, EOSC-hub, FAIRsFAIR, EOSC Enhance, DICE, EGI-ACE, C-SCALE, ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC Future). Annex 1 provides an overview of the contributions by SURF until the time of this writing.

Figure 1 Overview of projects contributing to EOSC developments⁸

To establish a governance structure for EOSC that is independent of the projects and represents the interests of the EOSC community, a new legal entity needed to be created. The EOSC Association⁹ was established on the 29th of July 2020 as a membership organisation with 4 founding members (i.e., CESAER¹⁰, CSIC¹¹, GEANT¹² and GARR¹³). The EOSC Association has since grown to over 200 members and observers. SURF is the mandated organisation¹⁴ representing the Netherlands within the association. To ensure further development of EOSC within the Horizon Europe work programme, the EOSC Association signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in July 2021 with the EC for the co-programmed European Partnership for EOSC¹⁵.

2.2 HOSA

HOSA stands for “Hoger Onderwijs Sector Architectuur” (Higher Education Sector Architecture) and started as a project in 2020. One of the aims of HOSA is to capture sector services that are important for strategic collaboration between various stakeholders into a single architecture framework. In the HOSA

⁸ Initial timeline diagram created by Hylke Koers presented at the 6th annual National eScience Symposium on 21 November 2019

⁹ <https://www.eosc.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cesaer.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.csic.es/en>

¹² <https://geant.org/>

¹³ <https://www.garr.it/en>

¹⁴ https://www.eosc.eu/members?field_status_value=organisation

¹⁵ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC_Memorandum_30_July_2021.pdf

domain architecture for Research Data Management v1.0¹⁶ the aim of the HOSA project has been defined as¹⁷:

The HOSA project aims to define an architecture for sector services that are important for strategic collaboration between higher education institutions, sector partners and market players. HOSA is therefore based on the optimal articulation of the sector's demand with regard to sector services. HOSA also provides a facilitating framework for interoperability between institutions and providers of common ICT services. HOSA will lead to current and new sector service initiatives more quickly and in a more future-oriented and future-proof way. Sector partners and market players in ICT services can easily respond to this with their service portfolio.

The scope of the domain architecture is the higher education sector with research universities, research institutions, and universities of applied sciences. During the start-up of the HOSA project, three topics were identified to guide the development of the domain architectures. The topics identified were:

- Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning (v1.0¹⁸, Onderwijs & flexibilisering)
- Research Data Management (v1.0¹⁹)
- Identity and Access Management (v1.0²⁰, Identiteit & Toegang)

Because the initial focus of EOSC is to support the scientific communities, the focus of this assessment has been primarily on the domain architecture for Research Data Management (RDM). The domain architecture has a time horizon for the medium and long-term of functional needs for sector facilities supporting RDM. This report will also touch on aspects of the domain architecture for Identity and Access Management, due to the fact that providing access to data and services is one of the main topics to be addressed in EOSC.

In the domain architecture for Research Data Management the aims are described as²¹:

Good, reliable research is becoming more and more important. Research outcomes are increasingly used to resolve social issues and to make social and economic decisions. In politics, too, more and more use is being made of outcomes from research. At the same time, the complexity and cost of research has rocketed.

The Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science has therefore worked with the sector to set a number of goals in the strategic agenda²². The main goal is to make research future-proof with the emphasis on collaboration (regional, national, international), alignment with society and regional integration. Independently from the higher education sector, goals such research quality and business continuity in education and research are attracting a lot of attention in the sector.

¹⁶ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-research-data-management-v1.0.pdf>

¹⁷ Reference 16, section 3.2

¹⁸ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-flexibilisering-onderwijs-v1.0.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-research-data-management-v1.0.pdf>

²⁰ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2023-01/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-iam-versie-1.0.pdf>

²¹ Reference 19, section 5, Introduction paragraph

²² *Strategische agenda hoger onderwijs en onderzoek – Houdbaar voor de toekomst*, Ministerie van OCW, Den Haag, December 2019

Based on this perspective, the higher education sector has set ambitions to keep research future-proof. The following sections describe these ambitions, which have a significant effect on the way research data in the future are handled.

Ambitions have been formulated on the following topics:

- Extend international collaboration
- Extend collaboration at the regional and national level
- Keep and maintain research as the cornerstone of society
- Open science
- Ensure research quality and internationally leading
- Safeguard research independence
- Ensure research continuity

One of the cornerstones within the HOSA domain architectures is the concept of business platforms. The book “Platform Revolution”²³ from Geoffrey G. Parker, Marshall W. Van Alstyne and Sangeet Paul Choudary, published in 2016, defines business platforms as:

Platform: A business based on enabling value-creating interactions between external producers and consumers. The platform provides an open, participative infrastructure for these interactions and sets governance conditions for them. The platform’s overarching purpose: to consummate matches among users and facilitate the exchange of goods, services, or social currency, thereby enabling value creation for all participants.

The concept of business platforms is not new, many commercial business platforms have been developed, for example, Uber, Bol and AirBnB. Also, within the research data domain initiatives have been taken to develop business like platforms, for example, the Amsterdam Data Exchange and the aforementioned European Open Science Cloud. Therefore, this concept is used because it provides insight into so-called online marketplaces, which arise in various places due to increasing cooperation in the sector.

²³ <https://wnorton.com/books/9780393354355/about-the-book/description>

3 Alignment

3.1 Principles

Within the scope of Enterprise Architecture²⁴, identifying and defining principles is one of the baselines within the architectural process. Architecture principles are defined as²⁵:

The underlying general rules and guidelines for the use and deployment of all IT resources and assets across the enterprise. They reflect a level of consensus among the various elements of the enterprise and form the basis for making future IT decisions.

Each Architecture Principle should be clearly related back to the business objectives and key architecture drivers.

Within the definition process of the HOSA domain architectures, there has been much emphasis on defining the architecture principles. These principles have been defined on two levels: HOSA high-level overarching principles²⁶ and domain-specific²⁷. The domain-specific principles are the concrete adaptations of the high-level principles for a specific domain.

Due to the evolution of EOSC over time, across different projects and initiatives, principles have been defined at different policy levels and to various degrees of details, as defined within the HOSA. To assess the alignment of the EOSC principles with the HOSA architecture principles, the following sources have been consulted:

- “COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe” principles defined in section I “Values and principles for research and innovation in the Union”²⁸
- “EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda” principles are defined in section 4 “Guiding Principles”²⁹
- “EOSC Rules of Participation”³⁰

Table 2 shows an assessment of the HOSA high-level and RDM domain-specific principles with both the EC Research and Innovation and EOSC principles. It should be noted that because the principles are described in different ways and are applicable on different implementation levels, no precise matching of the principles is possible.

²⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enterprise_architecture

²⁵ <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/togaf9-doc/arch/chap20.html> (section 20.2)

²⁶ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2021-11/hosa-overkoepelende-principes-v1.0.pdf>

²⁷ Section 3.4 Doelstructuur, see <https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-research-data-management-v1.0.pdf>

²⁸ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13701-2021-INIT/en/pdf>

²⁹ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V1.0_15Feb2021.pdf

³⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EOSC rules of participation*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541>

Table 2 Assessment of the HOSA high-level and domain-specific principles with EC Research and Innovation and EOSC principles

HOSA High-level principles	HOSA RDM Objectives	EC Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe	EOSC Guiding principles (SRIA)	EOSC Rules of Participation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An Efficient Ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid competition between organisations Engage collaborations with public and private sector Expand centres of expertise Expand practice-oriented research Avoid vendor lock-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Free circulation of researchers, support staff, scientific knowledge, and technology Pursuit of excellence – support research of the highest possible quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-stakeholderism EOSC will succeed if and only if it follows a multi-stakeholder approach Federation of infrastructures – EOSC will federate existing and upcoming research infrastructures (data- and e-infrastructures) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethics are guaranteed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital as a full alternative Ensure scientific integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uphold ethics and integrity of research and innovation Gender equality and equal opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Machine-actionability – EOSC will strike the right balance between machines and people in delivering the services that will serve the needs of European scientists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC is based on principles of ethical behaviour and research integrity EOSC users are expected to contribute to EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are viable 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value creation and societal and economic impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Federation of infrastructures – EOSC will federate existing and upcoming research infrastructures (data- and e-infrastructures) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC services align with EOSC architecture and interoperability guidelines
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are open 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support open Science Support citizen and crowd sourcing science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freedom of scientific research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Openness – EOSC will ensure that research artefacts are ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC is based on the principle of openness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessibility for everyone 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global outreach, Member States (MS) engage with joint 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FAIR principles – EOSC will enable research artefacts that 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC resources align with FAIR principles

HOSA High-level principles	HOSA RDM Objectives	EC Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe	EOSC Guiding principles (SRIA)	EOSC Rules of Participation
		activities with 3 rd countries and regions	are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are sustainable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic exploration of sector plans Strengthen regional role Develop a competitive portfolio to the US and Asia National policies towards knowledge creation and sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value creation – increase impact of research and innovation Coordination, coherence, and commitment – MS bring in the EU dimension in National research and innovation policies Inclusiveness – MS strive to develop the full potential of the European Research Area (ERA) to be competitive at global level Societal responsibility – striving to be responsive to society’s needs to expand collective capacities and achieve greater societal impact 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are solid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Portfolio management on themes³¹ 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC services align with EOSC architecture and interoperability guidelines
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are secure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure privacy for students and researchers Cybersecurity 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in EOSC is subject to applicable policies and legislation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector facilities are transparent 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC users adhere to terms and conditions associated with the resources they use
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs are deductible 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC users reference

³¹ The HOSA RDM domain architecture defined themes to support the research process: Smart Region platform, Smart Research Data platform and Open Research Tools platform

HOSA High-level principles	HOSA RDM Objectives	EC Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe	EOSC Guiding principles (SRIA)	EOSC Rules of Participation
				resources they use in their work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.surf.nl/files/2021-11/hosa-overkoepelende-principes-v1.0.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-research-data-management-v1.0.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13701-2021-INIT/en/pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V1.0_15Feb2021.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541

From the assessment, it can be concluded that to a large extent the EC and EOSC principles are aligned with HOSA high-level principles and RDM objectives. It should be noted, however, that the table shows gaps in which no HOSA RDM objective, EC and/or EOSC principle could be linked to a HOSA high-level principle.

3.2 Stakeholders

Within any architecture design process, you need to understand who the stakeholders are and in which role and capacity stakeholders are included within the architecture design. Within the HOSA RDM domain, the stakeholders are divided into 5 groups: investors, society, providers, research performing organisations, and individual researchers. Figure 2 shows the various stakeholders that are relevant for the HOSA RDM domain architecture.

Figure 2 HOSA RDM stakeholder diagram

To assess the stakeholders of EOSC, a similar mapping has been created by identifying key players within the EOSC ecosystem for the HOSA RDM stakeholders as in Figure 3.

Figure 3 EOSC stakeholder mapping

Comparing the stakeholder diagrams of HOSA and EOSC, there is much overlap in the key players from the different stakeholder groups except in the centre. The centre group within the HOSA diagram is identified as “instituten” (institution) while in the EOSC diagram it is described as “research performing organisations” with key players such as thematic cluster communities³², project and landmark communities listed on the ESFRI roadmap³³, communities organised as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)³⁴, and/or other mature organised communities (e.g. WLCG, LOFAR, WeNMR).

Research communities need to be identified as a separate group of stakeholders, because these communities are organised differently, transcend institutes, and operate at a national, European and/or global level. Research communities develop their platforms to serve their researchers. Depending on how the community is organised, the communities have commitments and/or agreements with member organisations and/or funding organisations to support their activities. Research communities participate extensively as organised communities within European calls, for example from the Horizon Europe work programme. Some research organisations have a strong institutional-based representation, for example Nikhef represents the High Energy Physics community and Astron represents the Astronomy community. Other communities such as the ERICs have a national representation, for example CLARIAH represents the Netherlands within the CLARIN ERIC and DTL is the representative of the Dutch Node within ELIXIR ERIC.

Within SURF, communities and researchers are identified as important stakeholders and are supported in different ways. This is not only through the services being provided to researchers, but also through the advisors supporting researchers to make efficient use of the services and perform their research as well as through domain specific community managers and collaborations with communities at national and international level.

³² <https://eosc-portal.eu/esfri-thematic-cluster-projects>

³³ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/browse-the-catalogue/>

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric/eric-landscape_en

3.3 Governance

In this section, a comparison is made between the organisational structures of HOSA and EO SC. In these organisational structures two governance layers are defined:

- Architecture governance: Is responsible for the definition and maintenance of the platform architecture and guidelines. Oversees compliance with the architecture guidelines but has no responsibility in the implementation.
- Platform governance: Is responsible for the implementation and operations of a platform and ensures compliance with the architecture guidelines.

Figure 4 shows the organisations involved in governing the architecture and platforms of HOSA and EO SC. In the next two sections the organisational structures of HOSA and EO SC will be described in more detail.

Figure 4 Comparison of architecture and platform governance within HOSA and EO SC

3.3.1 HOSA Architecture governance and platform Implementation

Architecture governance

The HOSA project was an initiative from the Architecture council of the SURF CSCs (Coordinating SURF Contactperson)³⁵. A SURF CSC is a contact person from a SURF member organisation who is responsible for coordinating and streamlining the communication between the member organisation and SURF. The CSC is appointed by the board of the member organisation; each member organisation can elect 1 CSC.

The Architecture Council (Architectuurberaad)³⁶ is a team of leading architects from SURF member organisations which has an advisory role to the SURF CSCs. The HOSA project originally started as an initiative by the Architecture Council to define an architecture for sector facilities that are important for strategic collaborations between higher education institutions, sector partners, and market parties. To support the development of the domain architectures, a steering group was established consisting of 6 representatives from the CSCs.

³⁵ <https://www.surf.nl/en/surf-members/coordinating-surf-contacts>

³⁶ <https://hosa.surf.nl/index.php/Architectenberaad>

As indicated in Section 2.2, HOSA comprises 3 domain architectures: Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning, Research Data Management, and Identity and Access Management. For each of these domains, a working group of experts has been established to develop the domain architectures under the guidance of the steering group.

Platform governance

While the HOSA architecture is governed through the CSC Architecture Council, the actual implementation of platforms conforming to HOSA must be seen independently from the governance of the architecture framework. The architecture framework provides guidance to the solution architects to develop the practical implementation. The governance in which the practical implementations are being developed and operated strongly depends on the organisation structure taking the initiative.

While such an initiative to implement a platform conforming to the HOSA RDM domain architecture has not yet been identified, a proposal in which the HOSA Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning domain architecture is a cornerstone has been accepted; see Nationaal Groeifonds funding program³⁷, proposal Digitaliseringsimpuls onderwijs NL³⁸.

3.3.2 EOSC Architecture Governance and Platform Implementation

EOSC Governance

The first initiative to establish an EOSC governance structure was to form an interim governance structure in 2018. The interim governance structure constituted of two bodies, the EOSC Governance Board (GB), with representatives from the member states and EOSC Executive Board (EB), with representatives of the research and e-infrastructure communities. The purpose of the EOSC EB was to oversee the EOSC implementation, provide advice on the way forward and on the implementation of the strategic and funding orientations, and assist with the transition beyond 2020. Much of the work during the interim governance period was done through working groups (i.e. Landscape, FAIR, Architecture, Rules of Participation, Skills and Training, and Sustainability³⁹). The interim EOSC governance established the EOSC Association as a governing legal entity and delivered the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), which provides a roadmap to achieve the vision and objectives for EOSC in the period 2021-2027. The EOSC interim governance was supported by the EOSC Secretariat⁴⁰.

After establishing the EOSC Association, the EOSC governance structure evolved into a tripartite governance consisting of:

- European Commission – representing the European Union
- EOSC Association – representing the European research community
- EOSC Steering Board – representing EU Member States and Associated Countries

³⁷ <https://www.nationaalgroefonds.nl/>

³⁸ <https://www.nationaalgroefonds.nl/projecten-ronde-2/digitaliseringsimpuls-onderwijs-nl>

³⁹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-working-groups>

⁴⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/831644>

The EOSC association has at the time of this writing 241 members⁴¹, of which 16 members⁴² are from the Netherlands. SURF⁴³ is the appointed mandated organisation from the Netherlands.

Architecture governance

The EOSC architecture has been one of the ongoing topics from the start through many of the EC-funded projects contributing to the development of EOSC. During the EOSCpilot⁶ project (2017-2019), initial proposals on the EOSC governance, policies, rules of participation, architecture, and Interoperability were formulated⁴⁴. Work continued in the EOSC-hub project⁴⁵ (2018-2021), and is currently continuing within the EOSC Future project⁴⁶ (2021-2023). In parallel to the EOSC-hub project, the interim EOSC governance and working groups³⁹ were established. While work in EOSC-hub was driven by project partners, the EOSC working groups were established independently from the projects. In general, the working groups were populated with representatives of member states. The EOSC Architecture Working Group (EAWG) was an exception to this approach, consisting of representatives from member states and from EC-funded projects.

After the work of the working groups was finalised at the end of the interim governance period, work continued via task forces⁴⁷ established by the EOSC Association. Members of the task forces are representatives from member organisations in the EOSC Association. The following task forces are of interest to the topic of the EOSC architecture:

- PID Policy and Implementation
- Rules of Participation and Compliance Monitoring
- FAIR Metrics and Data Quality
- Semantic Interoperability
- Defining Funding Models for EOSC
- Long-Term Data Preservation
- AAI Architecture
- Infrastructure for Quality Research Software
- Technical interoperability of Data and Services

Platform governance

As described above in Section 2.1, the initiative to develop EOSC was first mentioned in a blog³. The first cornerstones of the EOSC platform have been developed through projects such as EOSCpilot, EOSC-hub, eInfraCentral, and OpenAIRE Advance. As can be seen in Figure 1, these projects started before any official governance structure was established to oversee EOSC and the EOSC developments. In this period, the EOSC developments were steered by the EC and through planning of the Horizon 2020 Work Programme

⁴¹ <https://eosc.eu/members>

⁴² https://eosc.eu/members?field_country_value=Netherlands

⁴³ <https://eosc.eu/members/cooperatie-surf-ua>

⁴⁴ <https://eosc.pilot.eu/media/deliverables>

⁴⁵ <https://eosc-hub.eu/>

⁴⁶ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.eosc.eu/task-force-faq>

2016-2020 and the INFRADEV⁴⁸, EINFRA⁴⁹, and INFRASUPP⁵⁰ calls. In general, these EC-funded projects worked independently on the basis of the Description of Action (DoA) as defined in the Grant Agreement. Some collaborations across the projects were initiated and evolved in some cases into follow-up projects (e.g. EOSC-Enhance and EOSC Future) including the e-infrastructures (e.g. EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, OpenAIRE) and Research Infrastructures (RI) ⁵¹. Until the time of this writing, more than 30 projects have been contributing to the development of EOSC. Future support for developing EOSC is guaranteed under the Horizon Europe work programme 2021-2027 and INFRAEOSC funding calls.

At time of this writing, the EOSC-Core platform is being developed and operated by the EOSC Future project. Therefore, the current governance of the EOSC-Core platform is executed through the EOSC Future. Also at the time of this writing, the EC is preparing a procurement⁵² to tender for the EOSC-Core platform (i.e. Lot 1). The procurement is planned to be published before the end of 2022. After finalising the tender procedure, and the governance of the EOSC-Core platform will be transferred to the winner of the EOSC Core procurement.

3.4 Platform architecture

3.4.1 HOSA

One of the cornerstones within the HOSA domain architectures is the concept of the business platforms. The concept of business platforms is not new: many business platforms are available including some supporting the research data domain, for example the Amsterdam Data Exchange and EOSC. The main aim of the platforms is to support the demand and supply chain to ease the exchange of resources (e.g. services, content, knowledge, data) between customers and providers.

From a high-level architectural point of view HOSA has a layered architecture, as depicted in Figure 5:

- *Domain* – Strategic areas, transcending organisations, require a framework in which organisations can collaborate and share and exchange resources between providers and users within the domain.
- *Process* – The process layer defines four stages in the research process and identifies capabilities to be provided by the RDM platforms: define, prepare, execute, and utilise research.
- *Platforms* – The platforms support researchers with their research across institutes and focus on service provision that meets sectoral and public values.

⁴⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/infradev-04-2016> (EOSCpilot)

⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/einfra-12-2017> (EOSC-hub, OpenAIRE Advance)

⁵⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/infrasupp-03-2016> (eInfraCentral)

⁵¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/infraeosc-04-2018>

⁵² <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:234660-2022:HTML:EN:HTML&tabId=1&tabLang=en>

Figure 5 HOSA high-level architecture layering

To support researchers in the 4 different research cycle steps 3 platforms are defined for the HOSA RDM domain architecture:

- *Smart Region* – For the development of smart regions, ranging from local, and national to international regions, it is necessary to develop joint insight into the knowledge needs of the regions for now and in the future. The Smart Region platform offers opportunities to create and coordinate this insight with each other. Research themes are mapped out and defined based on data and data analysis. The platform offers opportunities for researchers to inform themselves about current research projects.
- *Smart Research Data* – With their campus, institutions form an important part of the development of society. All kinds of partners are already housed on or near the campus. In the digital world, the institution can take on a similar role. Good research data is essential for good research. With the help of the Smart Research Data platform, institutions can lay a foundation for the exchange of research data and thus for the development of a digital campus. Partners such as companies, governments and hospitals can establish themselves on this platform. The Smart Research Data platform supports the supply and demand of research data and offers services accordingly.
- *Open Research Tools* – For the processing, analysis, visualization, etc. of research data, specialist and often expensive services are required. It is undesirable for any institution to organize for itself, on the one hand from the point of view of keeping research affordable, and on the other hand from the perspective of collaboration. The Open Research Tools platform intelligently brings together various RDM services. Institutions can thus not only make their services available or use those of other institutions, but also those of partners. In this way, they strengthen the development of the digital campus and the region.

3.4.2 EOSC

According to the SRIA:

*EOSC is an integral part of the European Commission's strategy for realising the European Research Area, in particular the policy priorities of Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the world of findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data.*⁵³

On the basis of the FAIR lady report⁵⁴ from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group (ESWG)⁵⁵, proposing solutions for a sustainable EOSC, the EAWG⁵⁶ defined from their point of view the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE). This included proposals on high-level architecture diagrams describing the MVE, the EOSC platform, and capabilities of the core platform; see report *EOSC architecture working group view on the minimum viable EOSC*⁵⁷. The EAWG report on the MVE defines the MVE as follows:

As a result of the discussions, the Architecture WG defined the EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, EOSC Federation, and MVE as:

- *EOSC-Core: the set of enabling services required to operate the EOSC*
- *EOSC-Exchange: the set of federation services registered to the EOSC by RIs and clusters to serve the needs of research communities and the widening to the general public and private sector*
- *EOSC Federation: the set of scientific services provided by RIs and Clusters to the respective communities;*

The Minimum Viable EOSC is intended as a dynamic set of EOSC resources:

- *The subset of EOSC resources necessary for forming the added value and opportunities considered essential to be provided by the EOSC at a given moment in time, i.e. to allow essential services and research products (e.g. publications, datasets, software) to be discovered, composed, accessed and analysed via the EOSC, which could not be otherwise;*
- *The subset of EOSC-Core components/services required to operate and deliver such resources.*

The architecture diagrams on the MVE and EOSC platform are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

⁵³ SRIA page 39, paragraph 1.

⁵⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC: a FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>

⁵⁵ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/sustainability-working-group>

⁵⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/architecture-working-group>

⁵⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Sanden, M., Robertson, D., Appleton, O., et al., *EOSC architecture working group view on the minimum viable EOSC: Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/492370>

Figure 6 High-level diagram of the EOSC depicting the relationship between EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, EOSC-Federation, and the MVE

Figure 7 Architectural diagram illustrating EOSC-Core functions supporting the EOSC

Within the EOSC Future project, the next iteration has been made to further define EOSC focusing on EOSC architecture, EOSC-Core, and EOSC-Exchange. This has resulted in the architecture diagram depicted in Figure 8 and described in deliverable D3.2a on the “EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework”⁵⁸.

Figure 8 EOSC Future architecture diagram of the EOSC platform, including the relationship between platforms from thematic clusters, regional projects and resources provided through e-infrastructures and projects funded through the EC via the INFRAEOSC-07 call

This high-level architecture for EOSC proposed by EOSC Future comprises the following elements:

- **EOSC-Core** is the set of internal services which allow EOSC to operate. It includes a core technical platform that facilitates EOSC operations, upon which the researcher-facing resources in the EOSC-Exchange can rely and integrate as appropriate. It also includes non-technical coordination

⁵⁸ <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/EOSC-Future-WP3-GEANT-D3.2a-EOSC-Architecture-and-Interoperability-Framework-2021-12-22.pdf>

functions, such as the onboarding and security coordination, which operate and facilitate the technical platform.

- **EOSC-Exchange** is the set of federation services and other resources registered into the EOSC by Research Infrastructures and Science Clusters to serve the needs of research communities and the widening to the public and private sectors. Generic services and resources which target heterogeneous scientific domains and research communities are identified as Horizontal Services. Resources that target users from a specific science, community and/or regional domain are identified as Thematic and/or Regional Resources. The capability to compose resources across horizontal and thematic and/or regional resources in compliance with the EOSC Interoperability Framework is defined as the Execution Framework. While it is expected that the majority of the Horizontal Services are provided by the e-Infrastructures (e.g., EGI, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, GÉANT), generic services and resources offered by the Science Cluster communities will also be offered as a horizontal service.
- **EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)** provides the procedures and services required to support a flexible framework of standards and guidelines that facilitate the interoperability and composability of EOSC resources in the EOSC-Exchange via the EOSC-Core. As such, it leverages a semantic overlay where EOSC resources can be associated with the standards and guidelines (the IFs) they comply with, and therefore, be related by composability and interoperability features, across communities and providers. The EOSC IF is defined as a Reference Architecture Framework, which enables and governs:
 - A ‘System of Systems’ EOSC-Core architecture, via consultation and consolidation with the communities: the set of interoperability guidelines required for EOSC Providers to engage with the EOSC-Core and benefit from its added value services;
 - A registry database of EOSC Interoperability Guidelines as defined, used and proposed by the communities, enables providers to specify the interoperability boundary of EOSC resources and oversee the interoperability frameworks adopted by communities.
- **EOSC Support activities** sit alongside the EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange, and comprise the training, engagement, and other human-centric activities which make EOSC more attractive and easier to use and help users benefit from it more easily once engaged.

The aim of EOSC is to federate existing RI and e-infrastructures into a “System of Systems”⁵⁹ and make services and research products (e.g. publications, research data, software, and other research artefacts) available in a Web of FAIR Data and Services. Therefore, it is not the aim of EOSC to have a single platform, but rather to connect existing platforms developed and operated by the research communities and e-infrastructures, and to allow the discovery and access of resources (e.g. services and research products) beyond thematic and national boundaries. The EOSC-Core platform developed within EOSC Future must be seen as an overarching platform supporting cross-border discovery and access to resources beyond the local thematic and regional community. The overarching components are marked via the red square (i.e. EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, EOSC IF, EOSC Supporting Activities) in Figure 7. These overarching components are currently offered through activities within EOSC Future.

Platforms connected to the EOSC-Core platform include:

- **Science clusters and communities** will be embedded in EOSC through the work of EOSC Future but will continue to operate outside of the EOSC for their specific community. These include the **Science Clusters** (from the INFRAEOSC-04⁶⁰ call), the **Regional Initiatives** (from the INFRAEOSC-05⁶¹ call), as well as national communities, other research communities and less organised groups from the long tail of science and research. They will bring a rich set of resources to EOSC but will also have

⁵⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/System_of_systems

⁶⁰ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-04-2018

⁶¹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019

resources and other elements outside EOSC, which targeted their communities, including richer ontologies and domain-specific information and support.

- **EOSC provisioning projects** (i.e., EGI-ACE, DICE, OpenAIRE-Nexus, Reliance, C-SCALE) granted via the INFRAEOSC-07⁶² call are tasked to scale up the resource provisioning through EOSC. These projects' resources are available in the areas of distributed and cloud computing (EGI-ACE), data services (DICE), services supporting scholarly communication and open access (OpenAIRE), and additional research enabling services (C-SCALE and Reliance). The resources are made available "free at the point of use" for researchers and research communities. Providers within the projects offering the resources are reimbursed via Virtual Access⁶³ on the basis of actual usage.
- **e-Infrastructures** (e.g. EGI, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, GEANT) support researchers and research communities by offering horizontal services and resources through their member organisations. SURF is a member of EGI, EUDAT, and GEANT and is, at the time of this writing, registered in 6 services⁶⁴ offered through EOSC as a service provider.

3.4.3 Mapping of HOSA and EOSC platform components

Figure 9 shows a mapping of the EOSC platform components on the HOSA RDM platform architecture diagram. Despite the high-level architecture diagrams of HOSA and EOSC being different, because these are developed from either a HOSA or EOSC perspective, they show many similarities. Looking in more detail, all basic components of EOSC could be easily mapped on HOSA components.

Figure 9 Mapping of EOSC platform components on the HOSA RDM platform architecture diagram⁶⁵

3.5 Platform core components

In the previous section, a mapping was made of the EOSC platform components with the HOSA platform components. In this section, a comparison is made between individual platform components as in Table 3. Columns 1 and 2 of Table 3 describe HOSA platform core components from the "HOSA basisplaat

⁶² https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-07-2020

⁶³ http://www.rich2020.eu/tas_calls/about

⁶⁴ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?providers=175>

⁶⁵ An enlarged copy of this diagram can be found in Annex A

businessplatforms [root diagram business platforms]⁶⁶ with a short description taken from the HOSA RDM domain architecture document. Column 3 indicates the EOSC-Core components providing similar capabilities and column 4 provides the reference to the actual service offering the capability. Annex A describes a more elaborate version of Table 3 with an extensive description of the EOSC-Core components.

Table 3 Comparison table between HOSA RDM and EOSC-Core platform components

HOSA		EOSC Core	
Component	Description	Component	Example reference
Catalogue and Search Services	Provides a catalogue and intelligent search capability to search and filter content	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Service Catalogue Research Product Catalogue Single EOSC Portal Catalogue 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Service Catalogue: https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/ Research Product Catalogue based on OpenAIRE Explorer: https://search.eosc-portal.eu, https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/, https://graph.openaire.eu Single EOSC Portal Resource Catalogue in beta: https://eosc-search-service.grid.cyfronet.pl/ (planned to be released in Sept 2022)
Purchase and Licensing Services	Provides the capability to request and order resources (e.g. data and services)	EOSC Order Management System	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Operations Portal: https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/ EOSC SOMBO (Service Order Management Back Office): https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/sombo/eosc EOSC Metrics: https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/metricsEOSC/ServiceProvider
Financial Clearance Services	Provides support for easy payments of resources (e.g. services and/or data)	EOSC Virtual Access Funding Model	At this moment no clear and EOSC-wide funding model is available. The EC has been experimenting with EOSC-Hub and is experimenting in the INFRAEOSC-07-2020 projects, e.g. EGI-ACE, DICE, OpenAIRE-Nexus, Reliance, C-SCALE (https://eosc-portal.eu/5-infraeosc-07-2020-projects) with Virtual Access funding model
Service Request Management Services	Route a service request to the provider of a resource (service and/or data). Services offered have clearly defined service levels	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Resource Catalogue EOSC Order Management System EOSC Resource Profiles 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/ https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/ https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-resource-profile (e.g. ERP.MGI.3 ToU, ERP.MGI.4 Privacy Policy, ERP.MGI.5 Access Policy, ERP.MGI.6 Service Level)
Evaluation Services	Offers the capability for users to provide feedback on the services and research products	EOSC Resource Catalogue	Via the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace researchers can provide feedback via the review function: a rating can be provided between 1-5 stars and textual comments can be added. The feedback function is not frequently used: only 8 services out of 300+ received a rating, and only 1 service has 2 ratings/reviews
Metadata Management Services	Provides the capability to describe and/or collect relevant information from data and services from providers. The information will be used in the catalogue and during searches	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Provider Portal EOSC Monitoring EOSC Accounting: Services EOSC Accounting: Research Products 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/ https://argo.eosc-portal.eu/ Under development https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/

⁶⁶ <https://www.surf.nl/files/2021-11/hosa-inrichting-platforms.pdf>

Supply Connection Services	Provides an easy way to providers to connect data and services to the platform	EOSC Interoperability Framework	Initial guidelines for the EOSC-Core provided: https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC-Core+services . Other guidelines are under development
Orchestration Services	Allows easy connection between the different components within the platform	1. EOSC CMBD 2. EOSC Messaging	1. Under development 2. Example implementation: https://msg.argo.grnet.gr
Platform Management Services	Provides an agreement structure and processes to ensure QoS within the platform on providers, services, and data offered through the platform. This capability also ensures continual improvement and the evolution of the platform	1. EOSC Onboarding Process 2. EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT) 3. EOSC-Core Agreement 4. EOSC-Exchange Provider Agreement 5. EOSC Catalogue Owner Agreement	1. https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-portal-onboarding-process 2. This process is, at the time of this writing, managed by the EOSC Future project T6.1. 3. Draft version available 4. Under development in EOSC Future T2.2.4 5. Under development in EOSC Future T2.2.4
		EOSC Core Helpdesk ¹	Helpdesk platform and support units to support incidents and service requests for the EOSC-Core platform services
		EOSC Core AAI Proxy ^{1,3}	AARC compliant AAI proxy which provides shared login capabilities to EOSC-Core services. Providing a connector for the EOSC-Core Platform services to the EOSC AAI Federation
		EOSC AAI Federation ^{1,3}	Providing a distributed federated AAI infrastructure which allows for sharing of login and access to services and data across EOSC
		PID for Services ^{1,2}	Provide a method to uniquely identify services in EOSC-Exchange and avoid duplication of services across catalogues

1. EOSC-Core components are not identified as a core component within the HOSA RDM platforms
2. EOSC-Core component is at the time of writing under discussion
3. EOSC-Core components are identified as a core component in the Identity and Access Management domain architecture (in development)

From Table 3, it can be concluded that the HOSA and EOSC platforms have similar aims and offer similar capabilities. It can also be concluded that within the EOSC-Core platform additional components (e.g. Helpdesk, AAI Proxy, AAI Federation, and PID for Services) are included which have not been identified as such within the HOSA RDM platform. Although the AAI Proxy and AAI Federation are missing components within the RDM platform diagram, they have been identified as core components of the Identity and Access Management domain architecture, which is at the time of writing still under development.

One other main conclusion should be made. Most of the EOSC-Core platform components have an operational instance running as in column 4 in Table 3, being developed and operated from within the EOSC Future project. While, at the time of this writing, the HOSA RDM platforms are mainly defined on paper. To make the next step to establish the HOSA RDM platforms as an operational platform, additional efforts and funding are required.

3.6 Platform offered services

One of the main aims of the HOSA platforms is to support the demand and supply chain to ease the exchange of resources (e.g. services, content, knowledge, data) between customers and providers. Table 4 provides an overview of the identified services planned to be offered through the HOSA RDM platforms with services registered within the same category offered through EOSC. The (#<number>) indicates the number of services, at the time of the assessment (July 2022), registered within the identified category.

Table 4 Mapping of services offered through the HOSA RDM platforms with services offered through EOSC

HOSA		EOSC Exchange	
Component	Description	Component	Examples
Data Download Services	The platform offers services to retrieve or link data available in other sources. For example, from sources from parties operating and participating on the platform	1. EOSC Data Transfer Service 2. EOSC Research Data as a Service	1. https://www.egi.eu/services/data-transfer ; https://fts.web.cern.ch/fts 2. In development
Data Visualisation Services	Platform offers facilities that support employees in processing this data (Data Processing Services). In addition, the platform provides facilities for analysing data (Data Analysing Services) and visualizing outcomes (Data Visualization Services). Depending on the data that is exchanged, the services may differ per platform. It is expected that the data processed in a Smart Region will require less intensive processing than in an Open Research Tools platform	Onboarded Visualisation Services (#6)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/visualization
Data Analysing Services		Onboarded Data Analysis services (#65)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/data-analysis NL examples: 1. https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/lofar-science-processing 2. https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/haddock2-4-web-portal
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Processing Services Data Computing Services 		Onboarded Computing Services (#49)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/compute
Metadata Services	The platform includes facilities that support providers in meta-dating their data (Meta-Data Services)	Onboarded Sharing and Discovery/Data Services (#36)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/data Examples: 1. https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/zenodo 2. https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2share
Data Publishing Services	For making research data available, for example in the form of research results, services are offered that support the publication of data (Data Publication Service)		
Current Research Information Services	Creating insight into the current research portfolio supports the platform by enabling links with the current Research Information Systems of institutions. The platform offers options for searching this information	EOSC-Core components are provided through the EOSC Research Product Catalogue, Open Science Monitoring, and Research Graph	Resource Product Catalogue based on OpenAIRE Explorer: 1. https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/ 2. https://graph.openaire.eu 3. https://search.eosc-portal.eu/
Data Anonymising and Pseudo	In some cases, data must first be anonymised or	Onboarded Anonymisation Services (#1)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/anonymisation

Anonymisation Services	pseudonymised before being offered via the platform		
Research AI Services	Artificial intelligence will increasingly be used in society, with research leading the way. In research, algorithms are created that act as the basis for artificial intelligence	Is not a specific service category	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?object_id=&q=artificial
Research Software Services	The researcher has the opportunity to find and obtain this specific software on the platform. The platform also supports the researcher in making such software available	Onboarded Sharing and Discovery/Software Services (#24)	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/c/software
IoT and Realtime Data Services	Facilities that enable connections to be made to IoT and real-time data flows (IoT and Real-time Data Services)	Is not a specific service category	Search on IoT: #42 Search on real-time: #0

From Table 4 it can be concluded that most of the identified services within the HOSA RDM platforms services can be found within the same category of the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. This does not mean that the services offered through EOSC are automatically suitable for Dutch researchers and therefore suitable to be offered through the HOSA platforms. The suitability of EOSC-offered resources and the conditions under which these services are offered need to be assessed on a case-by-case basis and can be on request from users of the HOSA RDM platforms.

3.7 Platform interoperability

In EOSC, to support users and providers to onboard resources within the EOSC Portal Catalogue and to connect providers and resources to platform components, the EOSC IF is being developed. The initial steps toward defining the EOSC IF were taken by the EOSC FAIR Working Group (EFWG) under the EAWG⁶⁷. The efforts of the EFWG and EAWG resulted in the EOSC IF report⁶⁸, describing the general principles that should drive the creation of the EOSC IF.

The scope of the EOSC IF is not to develop new standards, because many standards already exist, but to provide a framework and a channel to select standards and guidelines to be promoted within EOSC and to be adopted within the platform and within the resources of providers. To sustain and populate the EOSC IF, the EOSC IF needs to be governed and maintained and the EOSC IF processes need to be defined. The process to select the standards and guidelines to be promoted within EOSC is based on finding a rough consensus among stakeholders. Finding rough consensus is a general approach within standardisation bodies and ensures the highest adoption of the selected standards and guidelines.

⁶⁷ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-working-groups>

⁶⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., et al., *EOSC interoperability framework: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

In the EOSC Future project, a step forward has been made in establishing the EOSC IF. The project is establishing a temporary governance structure for the duration of the project to start populating the EOSC IF. After the project (i.e. September 2023), the EOSC IF will be handed over to the EOSC Association. In the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024, a call⁶⁹ is planned to establish a robust governance structure to coordinate the maintenance and operations of the EOSC IF, design a review process for the architectural building blocks, establish an independent multi-stakeholder Architectural Board, and support the development and adoption of standards.

As described in deliverable EOSC Future D3.2a on “EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework”⁵⁸:

The EOSC IF needs to provide guidelines for providers to connect resources to EOSC-Exchange but will also provide guidelines to be adopted within services made available through EOSC-Core, supporting the composability and integration of resources across boundaries. The diagram below shows the different types of composition, integration and interoperability that can be encountered in the EOSC landscape.

Figure 10 EOSC Interoperability and composability models

The diagram shows the elements of EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange, connected and supported by the EOSC Interoperability Frameworks and Support activities. Vertical arrows represent **vertical integrations** (integrating a resource with more basic and/or common resources and functions), while horizontal arrows represent **horizontal integrations** (connecting peer resources) to add value. These two categories can be further divided into subcategories represented with the letters A, B, C and D:

Vertical integrations:

- **Type A:** Support composability of a resource with resources from the EOSC-Core to make the resources interoperable in EOSC (e.g., make resources discoverable via the EOSC-Exchange, integrate with the order management system and helpdesk to lower the barrier of access and to provide support to the users). Type A

⁶⁹ HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-05: EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework, <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2023-eosc-01-05>

is related to the EOSC-Core; work to enable composability of Type A began in prior projects where prototype core services were delivered such as in EOSC-hub and EOSC Enhance. It adds significant value for users and providers, as it makes the user experience more coherent, and for providers, it adds value without them having to do further development or saves effort on developing the functionality themselves. This also occurs within the thematic clusters, as they create 'stacks' of resources themselves. EOSC Future will extend both efforts to make this a standard step for all sorts of resource providers.

- **Type B:** Support composability of a resource with Horizontal Services to enrich the resource with additional features and easy/elastic/on-demand access to EOSC resources (e.g., a materials science service from a Science Cluster is integrated with a horizontal cloud computing service from an e-Infrastructure). Type B has been pursued by horizontal service providers such as the e-Infrastructures, each of which seeks to engage with providers of thematic resources but needs to be broadened and shifted to being based on sector-agreed consensus approaches from the EOSC Interoperability Frameworks, rather than those from each provider.

Horizontal integrations:

- **Type C:** Support composability of resources based on horizontal resources from e-Infrastructures and clusters (e.g. a horizontal data management service from an e-Infrastructure is integrated with data management functions and data from a cluster, or integration between e-Infrastructure services from different organisations). Type C integrations are a relatively new occurrence: asking horizontal providers to work with each other and make their resources interoperate. This happened to some extent in EOSC-hub where peer organisations that provide different resource types integrated their offerings. It is also important that the new Horizontal Services coming from the INFRAEOSC-07 projects are integrated with existing Horizontal Services. Composability of this type already occurs to a great extent within the thematic clusters, which try and collect their resources into coherent platforms. They plan to extend some of these resources as new Horizontal Services which are 'generalised' to be fully horizontal.
- **Type D:** Support composability of cross-domain resources to create added-value solutions to handle complex scientific problems (e.g., an epidemiological simulation service from one Science Cluster is composed of a rich data set on logistics and international trade from another Science Cluster to help track the spread of a global pandemic). Type D is perhaps the most challenging type of composability. This, like others, already happens within the Science Clusters and communities. For instance, inside EOSC-Life there is a significant diversity of research and supporting resources, but lateral connections between resources and datasets etc are possible and rational as all are in the same broad research domain. By connecting them and breaking down artificial or technical barriers, research is further supported and accelerated. Finding consensus across the larger EOSC community is even more challenging.

Because the HOSA platform approach is very similar to the EOSC platform approach, something similar as the EOSC IF is required to connect providers and resources to the HOSA RDM platform and to lower the barrier for users to make use of resources made available through the RDM platforms. Therefore, a similar approach can be taken to establish the HOSA Interoperability Framework with the same aim as the EOSC IF but scoped to the HOSA and to the Netherlands.

At the time of this writing, EOSC Future is starting up the governance structure and onboarding process to populate the EOSC IF, whereby zero guidelines have so far been onboarded⁷⁰. In 2023, the EC has planned a specific call⁶⁹ to further develop the EOSC architecture and IF.

3.8 Exchange of resources between HOSA and EOSC

As described in previous sections of this report, EOSC is not developed as a single central platform. The aim is to federate existing infrastructures in a "System-of-Systems" approach. The federation will be based on existing infrastructures as provided through the European and national e-infrastructures and by research

⁷⁰ 9 guidelines are at final stage and are pending on the availability of the EOSC IF registry, see <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+IF+Guidelines+overview>

communities. SURF is coordinating the national e-infrastructure for research and education in the Netherlands, offering access to various computing, data, and networking services. To offer Dutch researchers access to best-of-breed resources and tools to conduct research, it is essential to keep the national e-infrastructure internationally connected. The HOSA domain architectures present the evolution of the national e-infrastructure to a platform-based architecture. Therefore, it is essential to connect the national HOSA platforms to international platforms (e.g. EOSC, GAIA-X, Data Spaces). Connecting the HOSA platforms to EOSC allows access for Dutch researchers to resources (e.g. services and research products) made available through EOSC. Onboarding services made available through the HOSA RDM platforms provides researchers from Europe access to services and data available in the Netherlands, as depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11 High-level diagram describing the exchange of resources between HOSA and EOSC

To connect the HOSA RDM platforms to EOSC, and to onboard resources made available through the HOSA platforms into EOSC, the following aspects need to be considered:

- HOSA resources need to comply with the EOSC Rules of Participation⁷¹
- HOSA resources need to comply with the inclusion criteria of the EOSC Portal Catalogue⁷²
- HOSA resources need to comply with the resource maturity classification and need to have an EC Technology Readiness Level⁷³ (TRL) of 7,8, or 9
- HOSA provider and service descriptions need to be compliant with at least the mandatory fields of the EOSC Profiles⁷⁴
- HOSA Data Discovery Service needs to be made harvestable by the EOSC Research Product Catalogue

⁷¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EOSC rules of participation*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541>

⁷² <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-inclusion-criteria>

⁷³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

⁷⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-resource-profile>

- Clear conditions need to be defined on which HOSA resources can be offered to international users through EOSC

It is a strategic decision to decide which resources from the national e-infrastructure are made available through these platforms, conforming to HOSA, are made available through EOSC. At time of this writing, 10 service providers are registered with the Netherlands as a location, and these providers have onboarded 50 resources. SURF is registered at 6 services⁷⁵ as a service provider. These services have been onboarded by the e-infrastructures EGI and EUDAT and by Astron as the provider of the LOFAR Science Processing Service⁷⁶.

⁷⁵ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?providers=175>

⁷⁶ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/lofar-science-processing>

4 International architecture and platform activities

The current EOSC ecosystem has been predominantly implemented through development projects funded under the EC framework programme of Horizon 2020. The EOSC Association, and its newly created task forces, will represent the EOSC community and strategically guide the programming of development calls for EOSC within the context of the EOSC Partnership and under the new EC framework programme of Horizon Europe. There are, however, other international architecture, interoperability and business platform developments in Europe that are both relevant for EOSC and SURF, such as GAIA-X, NFDI and the common European Data Spaces. The key initiatives in Europe that are relevant for EOSC and SURF are depicted in Table 5.

Table 5 Overview of International initiatives on Architecture, Interoperability and Platform developments

Initiative	Scope	Involvement SURF
EOSC Future ⁷⁷	<p>EOSC Future is a 40M€ project aiming to demonstrate an operational EOSC Platform ('System of Systems') with an integrated execution environment consisting of data, professionally provided services, and open research products and infrastructure that will be accessed and used by European researchers who will be engaged, facilitated, trained, and supported to utilise EOSC resources and solutions</p> <p>The EOSC Future vision is centred around three key tenets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realisation of EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange with interoperable data and resources • Integration of data and resources from the science cluster communities into the EOSC-Core platform • Direct involvement of users in the co-design and implementation of the EOSC platform. 	<p>SURF is involved in different work packages, but is mainly involved in the tasks of defining the EOSC architecture and establishing the EOSC IF</p>
EOSC Association Task Forces ⁷⁸	<p>The EOSC Association has established 13 task forces organised under 5 advisory groups. The task forces aim to advance the implementation of EOSC on the specific topics and the gaps identified within the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). The following task forces are relevant for architecture and interoperability topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PID Policy and Implementation • Rules of Participation and Compliance Monitoring • FAIR Metrics and Data Quality • Semantic Interoperability • Defining Funding Models for EOSC • Long-Term Data Preservation • AAI Architecture • Infrastructure for Quality Research Software • Technical Interoperability of Data and Services 	<p>SURF is involved in the following task forces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher Engagement and Adoption • AAI Architecture • Technical Interoperability of Data and Services
Thematic Cluster Projects ⁷⁹	<p>The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) was established to shape collaboration in five thematic areas to pave the way for open access to data through EOSC. Through science cluster projects, supported by the INFRAEOSC-04-2018 call, ESFRI steers the integration and consolidation of thematic e-infrastructure platforms in preparation for</p>	<p>SURF is involved in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENVRI-FAIR • ESCAPE <p>In ENVRI-FAIR, SURF is involved in the ENVRI Hub catalogue and PID activities</p>

⁷⁷ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁷⁸ <https://www.eosc.eu/task-force-faq>

⁷⁹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/esfri-thematic-cluster-projects>

	<p>connecting them to EOSC. The five ESFRI cluster projects implement interfaces to integrate computer and data management solutions to create cross-border, interdisciplinary, and open cooperation spaces for European researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC-Life: Biological and Medical Sciences • ENVRI-FAIR: Environmental Sciences • ESCAPE: Astronomy and Accelerator-based Particle Physics • SSHOC: Social Sciences and Humanities • PANOSC: Photon and Neutron Physics <p>In the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024, a new call is being planned for the thematic clusters: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01 - Build on the science cluster approach to ensure the uptake of EOSC by research infrastructures and research communities</p>	<p>In ESCAPE, SURF is involved in supporting our High Energy Physics (HEP/WLCG) and Radio Astronomy (LOFAR) communities.</p>
Regional Projects ⁸⁰	<p>Five regional EOSC-related Horizon 2020 projects, supported by the INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 call, are collaborating to enhance synergies in all mutual activities related to the EOSC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC Nordic: FI, SE, NO, DK, IS, EE, LV, LT • EOSC Pillar: AU, BE, FR, DE, IT • EOSC Synergy: ES, PT, UK, CZ, SK, PL, NL, DE • NI4OS: AL, AM, BA, BG, HR, CY, GE, GR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI • EXPANDS: Photon and Neutron, complementary to the PANOSC project <p>Specific areas for cooperation have been identified to develop a common strategy to synchronise activities within the wider EOSC ecosystem.</p>	<p>SURF is not involved in any of the regional projects. The Netherlands is represented in EOSC Synergy by DANS</p>
FAIRCORE4EOSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIRCORE4EOSC is a 10M€ project focusing on the development and realisation of core components for EOSC. The project will support the implementation of a FAIR EOSC and address gaps identified in the SRIA. Leveraging existing technologies and services, the project will develop nine new EOSC-Core components aimed to improve the discoverability and interoperability of an increased amount of research outputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EOSC Research Discovery Graph ○ EOSC PID Graph ○ EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry ○ EOSC PID Meta Resolver ○ EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit ○ EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service ○ EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors ○ EOSC Software Heritage Mirror 	<p>SURF is involved in the project as the chair of the Technical Steering Group and in most of the work packages and tasks. SURF is developing the EOSC RAiD Service⁸¹ and participates through the Open Knowledge Base initiative in the use case on national research information systems</p>
GAIA-X ⁸²	<p><i>Gaia-X aims to establish a data space ecosystem, whereby data is shared and made available in a trustworthy environment. It is designed to give control back to the users by retaining digital and data sovereignty. It is not another cloud service but a trust framework system, linking many cloud service providers and users in a transparent, open environment that will drive the European data economy of tomorrow.</i></p>	<p>SURF is a member of the GAIA-X consortium. GAIA-X has in total 11 members from the Netherlands, including AMS-IX, EGI, Philips, TNO, and UvA</p>

⁸⁰ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-regional-projects>

⁸¹ Developing the Research Activity Identifier service (<https://www.raid.org.au/>) developed by ARDC to an EOSC Core service

⁸² <https://gaia-x.eu/>

	<p><i>Gaia-X aims at providing 4 core elements:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federation Services: A new model of cloud data knowledge, exchange, and trust not concentrated in single spaces or owners, bringing the control back to the user. • Standards: A specific set of standards to enable portability, interoperability, and connectivity interconnecting all actors in the data sharing and storage chain. • Data Spaces: The data relationship Gaia-X creates and enables between its trusted members when adhering to the same high standards and guidelines, and ultimately evolving to a data storage and sharing ecosystem. • Business Services: The provision of specific digital services that set common rules for collaboration within and across sectors and conform to the Gaia-X standard.⁸³ 	
European Data Spaces ⁸⁴	<p>The EC is spearheading the development of common European Data Spaces in strategic economic sectors and domains of public interest. These sectors or domains are those where the use of data will have a systemic impact on the entire ecosystem, including SMEs and citizens. This should lead to the availability of large pools of data in these sectors and domains, combined with the technical tools and infrastructures necessary to use and exchange data, as well as appropriate governance mechanisms.</p> <p>9 initial European Data Spaces have been defined: Health, Industrial and Manufacturing, Agriculture, Finance, Mobility, Green Deal, Energy, Public Administration, and Skills</p> <p>A Smart Middleware Platform is being procured with a budget of 65M€ to support the European Data Spaces through the Digital Europe Work Programme⁸⁵</p>	SURF is currently not involved in this initiative
NFDI ⁸⁶	<p>The aim of the German national research data infrastructure (NFDI) is to systematically manage scientific and research data, provide long-term data storage, backup and accessibility, and network the data both nationally and internationally. The NFDI guarantees funding of up to 90M€ per annum for 10 years to support such activities and will bring multiple stakeholders together in a coordinated network of consortia tasked with providing science-driven data services to research communities</p> <p>The NFDI's funding programme aims for consortia include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of data handling standards, procedures, and guidelines in close collaboration with the community • Development of cross-disciplinary metadata standards 	SURF is not directly involved in NFDI

⁸³ <https://gaia-x.eu/what-is-gaia-x/>

⁸⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066> (A European strategy for data, pillar D)

⁸⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/repository/document/2021-46/C_2021_7914_1_EN_annexe_acte_autonome_cp_part1_v3_x3qnsqH6g4B4JabSGBY9UatCRc8_81099.pdf (p22 section 2.1.1)

⁸⁶ <https://www.nfdi.de/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of reliable and interoperable data management measures and services tailored to the needs of the community • Increased reusability of existing data, also beyond subject boundaries • Improved networking and collaboration with partners outside the German academic research system with expertise in research data management • Involvement in developing and establishing generic cross-consortia services and standards in research data management together with other consortia 	
<p>HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-05: EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework⁸⁷</p>	<p>The aim of this call is to ensure that EOSC architecture and interoperability is built, encouraged, and maintained with structure, fairness, and transparency</p> <p>Achieving interoperability is essential to federate services, integrate data, and enable interoperation with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. The EOSC EOSC IF will provide the procedures and services required to support a flexible framework of standards and guidelines that facilitate the interoperability and composability of EOSC resources in the EOSC-Exchange via the EOSC-Core. The overall EOSC architecture should be overseen by an independent Architecture Board</p>	<p>SURF has been involved in the architecture and interoperability developments leading to this call through the EAWG, EOSC-Hub, EOSC Future, and in 3 EOSC Association task forces</p>

⁸⁷ Horizon Europe Work Program 2023-2024, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-3-research-infrastructures_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

5 Recommendations

5.1 Include Research communities as stakeholders

As identified in Section 3.2, research communities are organised differently, transcend institutes, and operate at national, European and/or global levels. Research communities act independently from the institutes at which the researchers are employed. Therefore, it is proposed to submit a change request to update the HOSA RDM stakeholder diagram to include “research communities” as a targeted stakeholder. During the workshop on Principles, Stakeholders, and Governance, there was initial discussion and a lack of clarity on where to place research communities in the stakeholder diagram. Research communities are overarching to organisations, are represented by research performing organisations (e.g. NOW-I institutes) and/or are represented by a legal entity (e.g. an ERIC). Research communities are depicted as a separate group, next to Institutes, within the stakeholder diagram, see Figure 12.

Figure 12 HOSA RDM stakeholders diagram including research communities

5.2 Going from paper to practice

The HOSA is an architecture framework for the Higher Education and Research Domain. At the time of this writing, the HOSA framework contains 3 domain architectures (i.e. *Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning*, *Research Data Management*, and *Identity and Access Management*). An architecture framework and platform-based defined domain architectures will not implement the platforms by themselves or guarantees uptake of the platform by the providers. To develop the platform, and the platform components to connect providers and resources to the platform, additional targeted funding is needed.

Recently, in April 2022, the project^{88,89} “Digitalseringsimpuls onderwijs NL [Digital Transformation Impulse for Education]” has been granted through the Nationaal Groeifonds⁹⁰ programme to advance education, to increase the flexibility of education, and to improve the digital skills of students and educators. The HOSA

⁸⁸ <https://www.nationaalgroeifonds.nl/projecten-ronde-2/digitaliseringsimpuls-onderwijs-nl>

⁸⁹ <https://www.digitaliseringsimpuls.nl/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.nationaalgroeifonds.nl/>

is one of the cornerstones to develop such a national ICT infrastructure and the “Digitalseringsimpuls onderwijs NL” programme will support the realisation of digital sector facilities conforming to the HOSA domain architecture on *Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning*.

As depicted in the timeline overview of EOSC in Figure 1, many funding calls at the European level under Horizon2020 have been contributing to the development of EOSC. At the time of this writing, the EC is preparing a procurement⁹¹ to fund the operations of the EOSC-Core Platform and some horizontal services and resources. Via the Horizon Europe work programmes⁹², substantial funding will be made available to continue the development of the EOSC-Core Platform and to support the uptake of EOSC by research communities and other stakeholders. The EOSC Association Task Force on Financial Sustainability⁹³ is furthermore developing a proposal for long-term financial sustainability of the main building blocks of EOSC.

Figure 13 shows a schematic overview of the major projects supporting the development of the EOSC-Core (i.e. EOSC Future⁹⁴) and the EOSC Association (i.e. EOSC Focus⁹⁵). As indicated in the previous paragraph, the future operations of the EOSC-Core are being tendered.

Figure 13 Overview of EOSC-related projects supporting the EOSC Association and EOSC-Core developments and operations

From the experience in EOSC, the resources made available through the platform are predominantly existing resources. What is missing is the platform itself and the connection of the resources to the platform. Additional funding is needed to support the development and realisation of the HOSA RDM platforms and to ensure a critical mass for the uptake of the platforms. A similar approach could be taken, as done within the education domain, of submitting a project proposal to the Groeifonds programme,

⁹¹ <https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:234660-2022:TEXT:EN:HTML>

⁹² https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/research-infrastructures_en

⁹³ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/financial-sustainability>

⁹⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/news/boosting-eosc-support-eosc-focus-project>

which is planning a 3rd round⁹⁶ of proposals with a submission deadline of February 3rd of 2023. If the 3rd round of proposals is considered opportune, work to prepare the proposal and to construct a consortium among national stakeholders (e.g. NPOS, research communities and RPOs) needs to start soon. Next to a Groeifonds proposal, other opportunities need to be assessed, for example, to support alignment between the HOSA RDM and the National Program Open Science (NPOS)⁹⁷.

5.3 Interoperability framework to promote guidelines and standards

As described in Section 3.7, the EOSC IF is being established to support the interoperability and composability of services and data across communities, RIs, and e-infrastructures in EOSC. The aim of the EOSC IF is to promote common standards and guidelines, not to make them mandatory, as many communities have already existing standards and established working practices.

One of the aims of the HOSA domain architecture is to support the interoperability between organisations, providers, and services and the exchange of research products such as publications, datasets, software, and other research artefacts in the Netherlands. To connect services from providers to the HOSA RDM platform “Supply Connection Services” are being planned. For providers to connect to the HOSA Supply Connection Services, standards need to be defined and guidelines need to be developed. To indicate which standards and guidelines are to be used within the HOSA RDM platforms, a similar approach as in EOSC can be taken to establish the HOSA Interoperability Framework, containing clear references to standards and guidelines to be used.

As described in Section 3.3, HOSA has via the “CSC Architecture Council” and CSCs of participating institutes strong commitment from the stakeholders. The HOSA IF could be established and governed via the “CSC Architecture Council” and delegated to a team of experts to manage the HOSA IF. Establishing the HOSA IF does not require big funds, but rather requires commitment from the stakeholders. Establishing the IF does not automatically ensure a critical mass for uptake, which urgently requires additional funding. See section 5.2 for an example from the EOSC Future project, where thematic cluster communities are being supported to connect resources to the EOSC platform.

To keep the HOSA RDM platforms connected to EOSC and to European RIs and e-infrastructures, and to prevent reinventing the wheel, it is recommended to review standards and guidelines onboarded within the EOSC IF before developing new ones. This especially holds for the standards and guidelines to make resources available through HOSA and EOSC, for example adopting the EOSC Profiles⁹⁸ to describe providers and resources within the EOSC Portal Catalogue.

5.4 Making services from the national e-infrastructure and of the HOSA platforms available through EOSC and visa-versa

As indicated in Section 3.8, it is a strategic decision to decide which resources from the national e-infrastructure and/or offered through the HOSA platforms are made available through EOSC. These decisions must be taken at the level of the SURF cooperation and must be supported by the Dutch government and national funding organisations.

⁹⁶ <https://www.nationaalgroefonds.nl/indienen-ronde-3>

⁹⁷ <https://www.openscience.nl/>

⁹⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation>

To be able to make these decisions, SURF should develop a policy and criteria stipulating the types and capacity national resources that are to be offered through EOSC. SURF should also develop a policy and criteria specifying the types and capacity of national resources that are to be offered to European researchers.

5.5 International engagement in architecture and interoperability

From Table 5 in Section 4 one can conclude that the topics of architecture, interoperability, and the development of platforms are international hot topics, similar to HOSA in the Netherlands. In the 3rd column of Table 5 SURF involvement has been indicated, including in different projects and architecture and interoperability activities. SURF participation in these activities has been mostly initiated through its involvement in European e-infrastructures (i.e. EUDAT⁹⁹, EGI¹⁰⁰, and GEANT¹⁰¹) and in supporting its internationally engaged research communities (e.g. WLCG, LOFAR, WeNMR, CLARIN). Therefore, the connection between national and international activities on architecture, interoperability, and platform developments has been limited until the initiative to develop this report.

To keep the national e-infrastructure, the HOSA platform, internationally connected, it is recommended to create a stronger relationship between our international and national activities on architecture and platform development, and to extend our activities internationally:

- Add an enterprise architect to the Enterprise Architecture team focusing on international architecture, interoperability, and platform activities
- Extend international activities in EOSC, GAIA-X, and the common European Data Spaces on the level of architecture and platforms
- Start up engagement with European SURF-like organisations on the level of enterprise architecture and national platform developments
- Assess participation in consortia for the call HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-05: EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework

⁹⁹ <https://eudat.eu/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.egi.eu/>

¹⁰¹ <https://geant.org/>

6 Conclusions

From the discussions during the workshops with the enterprise architects, and in developing this report, it can be concluded that HOSA and EOSC are very similar at the level of aim, principles, stakeholders, and architecture design. While the main objective of HOSA is to support higher education and research in the Netherlands, including access to international platforms, the primary objective of EOSC is to support researchers and research communities from a European perspective. The main differences between HOSA and EOSC are in the targeted audiences and the current state of practice.

Next to the difference between the National and European perspectives, a difference can be derived from the stakeholder mapping. The HOSA stakeholder mapping diagram (Figure 2) is defined around 5 identified groups (i.e. “Investors”, “Society”, “Institutes”, “Researchers” and “Service Providers”). A similar mapping has been created for EOSC, and while HOSA and EOSC generally target the same stakeholders, a difference can be identified between HOSA “Institutes” and EOSC “Research Communities”. As indicated in Section 3.2, research communities are nationally and internationally organised more independently across institutes, developing their platforms and services (e.g. RIs) to serve their researchers. While the HOSA stakeholder mapping identifies researchers as a separate group, (organised) research communities are missing from the stakeholder mapping. Therefore, it is proposed to include research communities as a separate group within the HOSA stakeholder mapping.

Another difference between HOSA and EOSC is the current state of practice. At the time of this writing, HOSA comprises three domain architectures (i.e. “Research Data Management”, “Flexible Education and Lifelong Learning”, and “Identity and Access Management”) without practical implementation. EOSC is more advanced, with a basic EOSC-Core platform available in which different core components are in production. This does not mean that the EOSC-Core platform is complete: the EOSC Future project aims to develop the EOSC-Core platform into a mature production platform. Also, via the Horizon Europe work programme, funding to sustain the operations and future developments of the EOSC platform is ensured. Via the Groeifonds programme “Digitalseringsimpuls onderwijs NL”, funding is ensured to realise the platforms proposed in the domain architecture “Onderwijs & Flexibilisering”. Funding is, however, missing to realise the proposed platforms defined in the HOSA RDM domain architecture. It is advised that national stakeholders (e.g. NPOS, research communities and RPOs) actively look for funding sources to support the development of the HOSA RDM platform components. Because the EOSC-Core platform is at the time of this writing more advanced, EOSC-Core components can be assessed and/or repurposed to realise a national platform on the basis of the HOSA RDM domain architecture.

At this moment, SURF has not onboarded services as a service provider into the EOSC Portal Catalogue. The services for which SURF is listed as a service provider are onboarded via the e-infrastructures EGI and EUDAT and by Astron. SURF needs to assess if and under which conditions services and resources can be made available to European users through EOSC. Therefore, it is advised to develop a policy and criteria for European resource provisioning and to make agreements with national funders and members to support access to resources from the national e-infrastructure for European users.

Architecture, interoperability, and platform developments are hot topics at the European level (e.g. EOSC, GAIA-X, common European Data Spaces), at the level of the research community (e.g. science clusters), at regional level (e.g. regional projects), and national level (e.g. NFDI). To keep national activities in the Netherlands aligned with international developments, it is important to be actively involved at the international level. SURF is via European e-infrastructures (i.e. EGI, EUDAT and GEANT) and via EOSC-

related projects (e.g. EOSC Future) already actively, but these involvements are more driven by international collaborations and supporting international engaged research communities. Therefore, it is advised to create a stronger relationship between SURF national and international efforts on architecture, interoperability, and platforms.

Annex A. Mapping of HOSA and EOSC Platform components

Figure 14 Mapping of EOSC platform components on the HOSA RDM platform architecture diagram

Annex B. Platform Core components

Table 6 provides a mapping of the EOSC Core capabilities with identified HOSA RDM core platform components. In the last column “Implementation”, when available, a reference is provided to the actual service offering the capability.

Table 6 Overview of the HOSA and EOSC Platform core components

HOSA Platform Core ¹⁰²		EOSC Core ¹⁰³		
Capability	Description	Capability	Description	Implementation
Catalogue and Search services	Provides a catalogue and intelligent search capability to search and filter content	EOSC Resource Catalogue: Services	The EOSC Service catalogues are a part of the overall EOSC Resource registry and catalogue ecosystem. A database of records, for providers, services and external catalogues, compatible with the EOSC Profiles specifications. Accessible via the Web from the Provider Portal, or the EOSC Provider Portal APIs to deposit or update provider and service records. It is a content provider to the Marketplace, Resource Registry or other connected catalogues (e.g. thematic and regional catalogues) and is exposed to researchers, research communities and 3rd catalogues.	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/
		EOSC Resource Catalogue: Research Products	The EOSC Research Product catalogues are a part of the overall EOSC Resource registry and catalogue ecosystem. The EOSC Research Product catalogue collects and interlinks EOSC research products (publications, data, software, etc.) and	Will be based on OpenAIRE Explorer and Graph services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/ • https://graph.openaire.eu • https://search.eosc-

¹⁰² <https://www.surf.nl/files/2022-02/hosa-domeinarchitectuur-research-data-management-v1.0.pdf>

¹⁰³ EOSC Future D2.5a Inventory of CORE Functions and Inclusion Criteria, <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/EOSC-Future-WP2-EGI-D2.5a-Inventory-of-Core-Functions-and-Inclusion-Criteria-2021-12-03.pdf>

			EOSC services with authors, communities, organizations, services, funders, and projects. The EOSC Research Product catalogue supports the onboarding (and validation) of EOSC research product profiles (collected from EOSC data sources) and of EOSC service profiles (collected from the EOSC Service registry). It also supports the discovery and navigation of EOSC resources, as well as statistics.	portal.eu/
Purchase & Licensing services	Provides the capability to request and order resources (e.g. data and services)	EOSC Order Management System	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC Operation Portals for Providers to manage Service Orders to collect metrics. 2. System to manage orders for services made through the central EOSC catalogue (Directly from a researcher-facing portal or potentially passed from other catalogues which display services pulled from the central catalogue). 3. Collect customer/user requests with relevant data, and pass them to providers via API, email, or other means. Support collection of order metrics. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC Operations Portal: https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/ 2. EOSC SOMBO (Service Order Management Back Office): https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/sombo/eosc 3. EOSC Metrics: https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/metricsEOSC/Service Provider
Financial Clearance services	Provides support for easy payments of resources (e.g., services and/or data)	EOSC Virtual Access funding model	<p>At this moment no clear and EOSC-wide funding model is available. The EC has been experimenting with EOSC-Hub and is experimenting in the INFRAEOSC-07-2020 (1) projects, e.g., EGI-ACE, DICE, OpenAIRE-Nexus, Reliance, C-SCALE (2) with Virtual Access funding model.</p> <p>(3) At the time of this writing the EOSC Association has a dedicated task force on developing a business model for EOSC. The objective of this Task Force is to produce by 2023 a proposal for long-term financial sustainability of the main building blocks of EOSC: EOSC-Core,</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-07-2020 2. https://eosc-portal.eu/5-infraeosc-07-2020-projects 3. https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfdefiningfundingmodelsforeosc_dr_aftcharter_20210614.pdf

			EOSC-Exchange and the Federation of Data & Data Services as defined in the FAIR Lady report "Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC".	
Service Request Management services	Route a service request to the provider of a resource (service and/or data). Services offered have clearly defined service levels.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Resource Catalogue (routing function) EOSC Order Management System (routing function) EOSC Resource Profiles 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> See EOSC Resource Catalogue See EOSC Order Management EOSC Resource profiles ask for either Term of Use or Service Level Specification, Access Policy, and Data Privacy Statement. In v3 these fields or optional but welcome become mandatory in v4. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/ https://opsportal.eosc-portal.eu/ https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-resource-profile (e.g., ERP.MGI.3 ToU, ERP.MGI.4 Privacy Policy, ERP.MGI.5 Access Policy, ERP.MGI.6 Service Level)
Evaluation services	Offers the capability for users to provide feedback on the services and resources	EOSC Resource Catalogue	Via the EOSC Portal catalogue (e.g., Marketplace) researchers can provide feedback via the review function, a rating can be provided between 1-5 stars and textual comments. The feedback function is not frequently used, only 8 services out of 300+ received a rating, and only 1 service 2 ratings/reviews.	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2drop?q=B2DROP
Metadata Management services	Provides the capability to describe and/or collect relevant information from data and services from providers. The information will be used in the catalogue and during searches.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Provider Portal EOSC Monitoring EOSC Accounting: Services EOSC Accounting: Research Products 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Provider Portal is the Provider WUI interface in which Providers manage the Provider and Resource descriptions. The ability to check the status, availability and reliability of EOSC service resources, both in the Core and in the Exchange. Supports the ability to monitor and observe EOSC resource availability as a measure of resource quality. Basic monitoring based on service endpoint or web page accessibility. Advanced 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/ https://argo.eosc-portal.eu/ Under development https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/

			<p>monitoring based on special probes developed as part of the integration with the resource.</p> <p>3. The ability to track and record usage of EOSC resources, i.e. research products and services, both in the Core and in the Exchange. Core service usage to show the uptake of Core services. Exchange service accounting is based on integration with thematic services and the Accounting service, to record service usage and show impact to funders.</p> <p>4. EOSC research product usage based on the aggregation of usage events collected, according to the COUNTER data usage metrics, from EOSC data sources.</p>	
Supply Connection services	Provides an easy way to providers to connect data and services to the platform	EOSC Interoperability Framework management	<p>A structure to manage, update, circulate and promote the EOSC Interoperability Frameworks, which are created through the projects and task forces to support and enable interoperability within EOSC. Interoperability includes technical, policy, process and administrative interoperability.</p> <p>IF areas include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource Description Framework - Open Science Policy Framework - Operational Support Framework - AAI Framework - Service Management Framework - PID Framework - Security Framework - Open Metric Framework- Procurement Framework - Data Access Framework 	Initial Guidelines for the EOSC Core provided: https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+IF+Guidelines+overview . Other guidelines are under development.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metadata Framework - Helpdesk Integration Framework - Other frameworks (TBD) 	
Orchestration Services	Allows easy connection between the different components within the platform	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC CMDB 2. EOSC Messaging 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Some of the EOSC Core Back-Office components (e.g., monitoring, service accounting, order management) need information about EOSC topology to properly operate. An analysis is underway to agree on a way to represent the topology for both EOSC Core and EOSC Exchange services and to select a component, acting as a Configuration Management Database (CMDB), where this information is stored. 2. The Messaging Service (AMS) is a publish/subscribe service, which implements the Google PubSub protocol. Instead of focusing on a single messaging API specification for handling the logic of publishing/subscribing to the broker network, the API focuses on creating nodes of Publishers and Subscribers as a Service. It provides an HTTP API that enables Users/Systems to implement message-oriented services using the publish/subscribe model over plain HTTP. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Under development 4. Example implementation: https://msg.argo.grnet.gr
Platform Management services	Provides an agreement structure and processes to ensure QoS within the platform on providers, services and data offered through the platform.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC Onboarding Process 2. EOSC EPOT 3. EOSC Core Agreement 4. EOSC Exchange 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A process that manages the onboarding of resources into the EOSC Catalogues. This process manages the onboarding of Providers, Services and Research Products (planned, under development). During the onboarding process, an assessment of the 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-portal-onboarding-process 2. This process is at the time of this writing managed by the

	<p>This capability also ensures continual improvement and the evolution of the platform.</p>	<p>Provider Agreement 5. EOSC Catalogue Owner Agreement</p>	<p>information provided via the provider and resource profiles is done. The EOSC RoP, EOSC inclusion criteria, resource maturity and mandatory fields of the profiles are leading.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. The EOSC Portal Onboard Team (EPOT) manages the onboarding process and performs regular audits of the Provider and Resource profiles. This process is at time of this writing managed by the EOSC Future project T6.1. 3. Agreement to be signed by the Providers of the EOSC Core platform components. 4. EOSC Exchange Provider agreement is a ToU to be accepted by the providers with onboarded resources into the Provider portal. The ToU describes the responsibilities of a Provider to maintain the resources within the EOSC Catalogue. 5. EOSC Catalogue Owner agreement is an agreement for Thematic and Regional catalogue owners willing to (automatically) onboard resources into the EOSC Catalogue, or visa-versa to register resources from the EOSC Catalogue into their catalogue. To ensure quality within the EOSC Catalogue, catalogue owners must comply, as a minimum, with the same inclusion criteria and maturity levels. 	<p>EOSC Future project T6.1.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Draft version available 4. Under development in EOSC Future T2.2.4 5. Under development in EOSC Future T2.2.4
		<p>EOSC Core Helpdesk</p>	<p>Helpdesk platform and support units to support incidents and service requests for the <i>EOSC-Core</i> platform services.</p>	<p>https://helpdesk.eosc-portal.eu (is planned to be migrated to a new helpdesk platform)</p>
		<p>EOSC Core AAI proxy</p>	<p>AARC compliant AAI proxy which provides shared login capabilities to <i>EOSC- Core</i> services.</p>	<p>https://aai.eosc-portal.eu (based on EGI CheckIn)</p>

			Providing a connector for the <i>EOSC-Core</i> Platform services to the EOSC AAI Federation.	
		EOSC AAI Federation	Providing a distributed federated AAI infrastructure which allows for sharing of login and access to services and data across EOSC.	Under development
		PID for services	Provide a method to uniquely identify services in <i>EOSC-Exchange</i> , and avoid duplication of services despite multiple entry points through which services can be onboarded (directly to <i>EOSC-Exchange</i> , via regional or thematic catalogues). This is a service for providers to mint PIDs for their services or for catalogue owners to generate and mint PIDs for services onboarded within EOSC-approved catalogues.	Under discussion, example services EUDAT B2HANDLE/SURF PID service, DataCite DOIs
		EOSC Collaboration system	Internal tools needed to coordinate EOSC- Core and Exchange operations. These likely include collaborative information management (e.g. a Wiki, document database), task and issue tracking (a ticketing system), and communication management (email, chat, mailing list, video conferencing). While individual organisations may have these capabilities, they will be needed at a larger scale to support EOSC-Core and Exchange operations.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wiki: https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/ 2. Ticket: https://jira.eoscfuture.eu